

Fertilizer management—inorganic

Effect of DCD on urea N uptake by rice and its balance in soil

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We conducted a pot culture experiment on the effect of dicyanamide (DCD) on urea N efficiency in lowland rice grown in the 1990 monsoon season (Jul-Oct). We used soil from the Mehrauli series in the non-acid, hypothermic family Typic Ustochrepts. The soil had pH 7.8, 0.44% organic C, and sandy loam texture.

In six treatments (see table) with three replications, 120 kg N/ha was applied as urea with or without DCD (10% of urea). We used urea with 4.987 atom percent excess ¹⁵N. Urea and DCD were mixed and then hydraulically pressed to form pellets. The crystalline urea and DCD were incorporated in the upper 2.5 cm of the soil; pellets were placed 2.5 cm deep in the center of the pots.

Three hills of two Pusa 33 seedlings were transplanted on 17 Jul into 20-cm-diam pots containing 7.66 kg soil. Water was kept about 4 cm above the soil throughout rice growth. Urea was applied

basally a week after transplanting; in the split treatments, the second half was applied 3 wk later.

Effect of DCD on urea balance in soil.

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Maximum grain yield was obtained where urea with DCD was applied as 1.1 g pellets at transplanting. Split-applied pellets gave better results than the crystalline form, but the increase was much less than that from pellets applied basally.

Applying the nitrification inhibitor DCD and crystalline urea to rice did not improve fertilizer N-use efficiency but did reduce gaseous N losses. This was

evident from the unaccounted for decline in N (see figure). Fertilizer N recovery by rice increased when urea N was applied in two splits, with or without DCD. Urea applied with DCD as pellets, either in full dose at transplanting or in two splits, resulted in the highest fertilizer N recovery by rice (41 %) and very little urea N loss.

Urea pellets without DCD must be studied to determine whether the increased yield and reduced N loss with pellets containing DCD was due to the large urea particles or to the presence of DCD. □

Effect of urea and DCD application on rice. New Delhi, India, 1990.

Treatment	Tillers (no./plant)	Yield (g/pot)		N uptake (mg/pot)	
		Grain	Straw	Grain	Total
T1: urea basal	7.7	18.5	24.1	185	300
T2: urea in 2 splits	7.3	21.2	25.7	221	340
T3: urea + DCD, basal	8.0	21.3	23.8	209	311
T4: urea + DCD in 2 splits	8.3	21.2	25.5	231	335
T5: urea + DCD, basal, as 1.1 g pellets	12.3	30.6	35.8	377	540
T6: urea + DCD in 2 splits; as 0.55 g pellets	9.3	25.7	36.1	283	460
LSD (0.05)		2.2	4.0	33	49

Crop management

Adverse effects of beushaning on intermediate deepwater rice (DWR)

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Rainfed lowland rice in eastern India is established mainly by broadcasting seed under dry soil conditions followed by interplant cultivation after water accumulates. Beushaning is the practice of plowing rice with a simple bullock-drawn plow without turning the soil, leveling with a ladder, and filling blank spaces with the uprooted plants.

Beushaning is widely practiced to control weeds in shallow water conditions, promote tillering, and check vertical plant growth to reduce lodging.

We evaluated the effects of post-establishment interplant cultivation with a hand hoe and beushaning under excess water conditions. Utkalprabha, a popular semitall, long-duration, photoperiod-sensitive cultivar was broadcast and line sown (drilled or dibbled) in dry soil on 28 May 1990 using 400 seeds/m². Fertilizers were banded in furrows before sowing at 40-8.7-16.7 kg NPK/ha. Treatments were arranged in a factorial randomized block design with three replications. Rice was cultivated between plants with a hand hoe at 25 and 40 d after emergence (DE) and beushaned at 40 DE in 44 cm water.